

Reproduce: Safe Deployment for Counterfactual Learning to Rank with Exposure-Based Risk Minimization.

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1 Introduction

In this work, we document our efforts to reproduce our assigned paper [1], which introduces a novel counterfactual risk minimization (CRM) method for safe deployment in counterfactual learning to rank (CLTR). The paper proposes an exposure-based risk regularization technique to mitigate the high variance issues associated with inverse propensity scoring (IPS) in CLTR, ensuring that learned ranking models remain close to a trusted safe model during deployment. The results in the paper suggest that this new method performs significantly better than other established methods as well as baseline methods. Our goal was to validate the papers claims by reproducing its experimental results. However, we encountered significant challenges during the reproduction process, including difficulties in running the provided code and interpreting the results. Despite these obstacles, we documented our findings and the issues faced, aiming to provide insights into the reproducibility of the paper’s methodology. This report outlines the setup of the original paper, our approach, the challenges encountered, as well as the lessons learned.

2 Paper Original Experimental Setup

2.1 Datasets

The three largest publicly available LTR datasets were used to do the experiment:

- Yahoo! Webscope [2]
- MSLR-WEB30k [3]
- Istella [4]

The datasets include queries, document lists, feature vectors, and manually-graded relevance judgments. A logging policy is trained on a 3 percent fraction of relevance judgments, simulated in a real-world setting for click-based optimization. The experiments focus on simulating real-world ranking systems using these datasets

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2.2 Algorithms and Techniques

A semi-synthetic experimental setup was employed to generate click data. Specifically, a logging policy was trained on a small subset (3%) of relevance judgments to replicate real-world scenarios where production rankers collect clicks for optimization purposes.

Clicks were simulated using a position-based click model, where the probability of examination was governed by a rank-dependent function:

$$P(E = 1 \mid q, d, y) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\text{rank}(d \mid y)^2} & \text{if } \text{rank}(d \mid y) \leq 5, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Relevance probabilities were transformed using the following equation:

$$P(R = 1 \mid q, d) = 0.025 \cdot \text{rel}(q, d) + 0.2,$$

where $\text{rel}(q, d)$ represents the manually graded relevance judgment. This transformation captures the sparse nature of click data in real-world systems.

2.3 Metrics and Evaluation Approaches

The evaluation metric used was NDCG@5, based on relevance judgments. Performance was evaluated on test sets for each dataset. Results were reported as averages over 10 independent runs, with statistical significance assessed using a two-sided Student’s t-test.

Additionally, the experimental results highlighted the robustness and efficiency of exposure-based CRM, demonstrating significant reductions in the amount of interaction data required for performance parity with baseline methods. This improvement underscores the method’s practical advantages in real-world deployment scenarios.

3 Reproduction Workflow and Challenges

For this project, we used the paper and the code provided by the authors as the foundation for our reproduction workflow. However, we faced several challenges related to dataset access, code compatibility, and computational limitations. Below, we outline the workflow, the challenges encountered, and the solutions we implemented to overcome them.

3.1 Dataset Collection and Preparation

The datasets used in this project were MSLR-WEB30k, Yahoo! Webscope, and Istella. However, obtaining and preparing these datasets presented several challenges:

- **Access to Datasets:** We requested access to the Yahoo! Webscope dataset but did not receive a response in time. Additionally, for the Istella dataset, only the train and test parts were available, while the validation dataset was missing. Since the validation dataset was necessary for successful execution of the code, we primarily worked with the first fold of the MSLR-WEB30k dataset.
- **Dataset Size Constraints:** Due to computational limitations, we sampled only 1% of the dataset for our experiments. We also limited processing to a single fold of the MSLR-WEB30k dataset. To sample dataset, we created `data_sampler.py`.
- **Missing Folders and Logs:** Essential folders, such as `CRM_project_logs` and `results`, were not provided. We manually created these folders and debugged the code to infer the necessary folder structures.

3.2 Code Setup and Modifications

The GitHub repository originally linked in the paper no longer contains any code and instead directs to a different repository hosting the code published alongside the authors' 2024 paper [5]. Since the 2024 paper appears to be an extension of the 2023 work, we decided to utilize this updated code to reproduce the results, which might allow us to validate their findings and ensure the reproducibility of their research. Setting up the code to be executed required substantial effort due to the following issues:

- **Outdated Libraries and Dependencies:** The `requirements.txt` file was outdated and did not align with current library versions. We resolved this by:
 - Updating `torch` to version 2.0.1 and `pytorch-lightning` to version 1.8.5.
 - Installing CUDA toolkit version 11.8 to ensure compatibility with PyTorch.
 - Manually installing missing libraries, such as `boto3`, `wandb`, and `jax`.
- **Code Modifications:** There were several necessary changes in the source code for successful execution:
 - In the `data_loader.py` file, Code line: 12, we had to import the `LTRLoggerDataLoader` module, as it is necessary for code execution.
 - In the same file, code lines 171–173, we modified the initial constructor call of the `DataLoader` class by adding the new parameter `pin_memory=True` to optimize GPU execution. Additionally, we reduced the `num_worker` parameter from 4 to 2 due to computational limitations.
 - In the file `logging_policy.py`, lines 213–221, we changed the initialization of the trainer object. The `Trainer` class in the initial code used the outdated parameter `gpus`. We replaced it with the parameters `accelerator = "gpu"` and `devices = 1`. The former specifies the use of GPU, while the latter defines the number of GPUs to use.
- **Missing JSON Files:** Certain JSON files referenced in the code were unavailable. These files were expected to be stored in the `results/test_results` folder, which did not exist initially. This issue affected the files `cltr_pytorch.py`, `cltr_pytorch_ppo.py`, `cltr_pytorch_dr.py`, and `cltr_pytorch_dr_risk.py`. To address this, we:
 - Commented out the lines in the code that relied on loading the missing JSON files. According to the source code, these files were used to extract information about learning rates, which were then used in the code.
 - Replaced the learning rate hyperparameters, such as `lr_risk` and `lr_ips`, with fixed values (e.g., 0.0001).
- **Folder Creation:** Missing directories, such as `CRM_Project_logs` and `results/test_results`, were manually created to store experiment outputs. This was done in the following way:
 - For `CRM_Project_logs`, although it is specified in the configuration file (`config.yaml`), the structure of the folder had to be inferred through debugging. After inferring, we determined that each dataset should have a folder named after it, and inside each folder, there should be an additional folder named `click_metadata_100`. For example, in the case of using the MSLR30K dataset, the folder structure should look like:
`CRM_project_logs/MSLR30K/click_metadata_100`.
 - For `results/test_results`, we had to manually create the folder. Inside this folder, there are sub-folders whose names were obtained by concatenating parameters passed through the command line. These sub-folders should have been dynamically created, but this functionality was missing. To address this, we added code to check if the folder exists. If it does not exist, it is created using the same concatenation logic. This modification was made in files whose names contain "`cltr_pytorch`".

- **.pk File Generation:** The documentation did not describe how to generate .pk files. Through debugging, we identified the expected format and created placeholder files to allow the code to execute. After executing the command for the logging_policy.py file, .pk or .pickle files were stored in the folder CRM_project_logs/{dataset} under the name logging_policy. Additionally, some log files are stored in CRM_project_logs/MSLR30K/click_metadata_100, such as alpha_beta.npy, test.pickle, and train_qid_map. Note: those files along with logging_policy were removed from our version of code, because of the maximum submission limitation to 10MB per file. They can be obtained by new execution of the first command provided within the README.md file.
- **WandB Integration:** To visualize the results, we created a new wandb account and modified the code to use our credentials instead of the initial creator’s credentials.

3.3 Experiment Execution and Computational Challenges

Running the experiments presented the following challenges:

- **Computational Limitations:** Memory constraints and execution delays frequently caused errors. To mitigate this:
 - We sampled smaller datasets (1% of MSLR-WEB30k) and optimized memory usage.
 - We leveraged GPU execution using CUDA 11.8 to improve processing speed.
- **Unclear Steps in the Workflow:** Some undocumented steps, such as generating .pk files and loading policies, along with undefined folder structure, required significant debugging and reverse engineering to identify the correct workflow.
- **Parameter Adjustments:** While we followed the parameters described in the paper, we made modifications to suit our computational constraints and ensured compatibility with the modified code.

Despite these obstacles, we successfully reproduced parts of the paper’s results using limited resources. These adjustments underscore the importance of comprehensive documentation and resource availability in reproducibility efforts.

4 Results and Reproducibility Assessment

The process of reproducing results was significantly hindered by missing details in the paper, particularly regarding data preprocessing, hyperparameter choices, and result interpretation.

We successfully implemented the provided Python code and ran it on a small sample of the dataset. This required substantial debugging and modifications, as the original implementation contained errors and inconsistencies not addressed in the paper. While we were able to execute the training process, interpreting the outputs remains challenging. The paper provides no explicit guidance on expected results, making it unclear whether our reproduced outcomes align with the original findings. While we managed to get the code running, the lack of detailed documentation and result interpretation prevents a full validation of the paper’s conclusions.

5 Conclusion

The reproduction of the paper’s results presented several challenges, including dataset accessibility, code compatibility, and computational limitations. While we successfully ran the provided code with substantial modifications, the lack of detailed documentation made it difficult to verify the correctness of the reproduced results. Adjustments such as

updating dependencies, modifying training parameters, and creating missing files and folders were necessary for successful execution. Despite these obstacles, we were able to execute a functional version of the code and obtain experimental results on a smaller dataset, demonstrating partial reproducibility of the paper's claims. These challenges highlight the importance of comprehensive documentation, the necessity for well documented code repositories, and the value of providing complete instructions starting from the acquisition of code and datasets until the results. These lessons highlight that for research to be truly reproducible, authors must ensure that all components of their experimental setup are transparently and thoroughly documented.

References

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